

A Study On The Dance Form Of Yangge In Hebei, China

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Abstract

The development of the Yangge is closely related to human activities. At first, the Yangge was a repertoire hummed by people during labor, initially to relieve fatigue, and in the subsequent development it further absorbed various arts such as agricultural songs, rhizomes, and operas, and gradually became a folk dance with performance nature, which was liked by people. Yangge is a typical folk dance of the Han people, and is a key component of the life of the Han people. In a broad sense, Yangge refers to the folk dance that includes activities such as "walking meeting" and "social fire"; in a narrow sense, there are two main types of Yangge, the first one is Yangge (also called ground Yangge) and the second one is Yangge on stilts, the former one does not have the item of stilts, but is danced on the flat ground. Yangge is also called differently in the north and south of China, and in the south it is called "flower drum" and "tea picking". Hebei folk dance has a long history, the population flow between the various ethnic groups, many ethnic dance and music culture blend with each other, gradually evolved into the performance form of singing and dancing. The first one is Changli Yangge, the second one is Cangzhou Luzi, and the third one is Jingfu Lahua. In 2006 and 2008, these types of rice-songs were selected to be included in the national list of non-patrimonial heritage. In this thesis, the above three types of rice-songs are the main objects of the study, supplemented by some regional rice-songs to analyze the form of rice-song dance, to show the characteristics of Hebei dance, and to lay the theoretical foundation for the protection of non-heritage culture. The research content of this thesis is divided into the following four main contents: First, the living space of Hebei Yangge, from the natural ecological environment and human ecological environment to explain the influence of regional culture on the art form of Yangge, the living environment and customs of the folk determine the activity space of Yangge. Second, the dance form of Hebei Yangge, through field survey and Laban movement analysis mainly on the dance movement and performance characteristics to analyze and elaborate, from the dance ontology to typical movement form, role style, dance composition, props use several aspects of detailed analysis, so as to show the way of life of the villagers and folklore concept. Third, from the two aspects of music and costume and prop characteristics, the traditional Yangge performance is studied, and the villagers' needs and aesthetic demands reflected in the Yangge performance are discussed. Four, Hebei Yangge cultural form interpretation, from the historical cultural form characteristics, geographical cultural form characteristics, folklore perspective of the development of Hebei Yangge and stage creation of cultural form four directions to discuss, Hebei Yangge in the social process of change, explore the value of the art of Yangge in the context of the new era.

Introduction

At present, the theoretical results related to this research are all domestic research results, which have not been available outside of China. Therefore, this research is limited to the territory of China. Through the collation of relevant information, it is concluded that there are many theoretical results about Hebei Yangge, but they are mostly focused on the research of picking, excavating and finishing of each single Yangge, such as: Di Yangge and Jingfu Lahua. However, there are few studies on the style, form, and characteristics of representative rice-songs in Hebei area in common time and in time. There are also few studies on the cultural forms of Hebei Yangge from dance forms and movements. The focus of this thesis is on the field survey, combined with the literature, and through the Laban dance score and movement analysis, a more in-depth investigation of the dance form movement, and finally analyze the cultural form of Hebei Yangge contained in the dance movement itself.

Hebei dance has a long history. The "Mud River Bay" is the cradle of the origin of human beings in the East 2 million years ago, and this hot land has given birth to the bright pearl of "Hebei dance". Since ancient times, there are many ethnic types in the Hebei region, and different cultures have intermingled to produce the Hebei dance with strong characteristics. The author conducts a literature review according to three aspects: historical origin, dance ontology, and the development of "non-heritage" dance heritage.

Historical origin

The History of Yanzhao Literature and Arts"tells the history of Yanzhao literature and arts from ten aspects: literature, drama, film and television, music, dance, opera, acrobatics, calligraphy, art, and photography, which helps the author to clarify the connection between dance and other art disciplines and provides a certain basis for subsequent research; "The Complete Book of Chinese Folk Tales - Hebei" introduces the folk cultural phenomenon in Hebei from folk myths, legends, stories, and jokes, and provides a basis for the origin and legends of the Yangtze. The book introduces the folk culture phenomena in Hebei from folk myths, legends, stories and jokes, providing a basis for the sources and legends of Yangge; The History of Chinese Dance studies the development process of Chinese dance from primitive society to the present and its laws, reflecting the ideology, ideology and emotion and cultural connotation of the period through the dance phenomena in different historical stages, providing a favorable help to study the historical background of Hebei dance. The History of Hebei Dance presents in detail the whole process of the occurrence and development of dance in the hot land of Hebei. From the testimony of human activities in ancient times to the dazzling and colorful Hebei dances of today, the process of the times reveals the inclusive and cultural spirit of Hebei dances. Through the Xia, Shang and Zhou Dynasties, Hebei dance gradually flourished; the development of music and dance in the Han Dynasty led to the rapid development of Hebei folk dance; at the stage of the Wei, Jin and North and South Dynasties, the intermingling of various ethnic groups was presented, and 12 dynasties were successively passed, with frequent cultural exchanges between various ethnic groups and the intermingling of music and dance; in the Tang Dynasty, the culture of dance and music developed rapidly and produced many works that have remained famous for ages. In the Song Dynasty, the music and dance of the Tang Dynasty continued to develop, and the folk dance of Hebei was influenced by the culture of the Central Plains in the Liao Dynasty, which formed an inclusive character; in the Ming and Qing Dynasties, the folk dance of Hebei was influenced by Chinese opera and gradually evolved into the performance form of singing and dancing. The Republican period was a fertile ground for the development of revolutionary literature and art, and the region was not only the main front in the anti-Japanese war, but also an important place in the liberation war. Therefore, a large number of widely circulated literary works were born during this period; after entering New China, the ritual function of folk dances in the region continued to diminish and almost died out. After the reform and opening up, the development of traditional culture has been highly respected, especially the establishment of the protection of non-heritage, so that folk dances have been reborn again. The representative folk dances in Hebei are the Diyangge, Lahua, Cangzhou Luzi, Xushui Lion Dance, Nuo Dance, Dragon Dance, Flower Carrying Kongs, Zhaozi Drum, Wu'an Dry Boat, and Piyong. The unprecedented development of dance and rapid urbanization in this period allowed Hebei folk dance to develop faster and gradually form its own pattern. Professionalism developed rapidly, presenting a large number of dance works as well as dancers. External dance activities and exchanges have flourished, dance research levels have increased, and theory has developed rapidly. This book records in some detail the dance phenomena that took place in Hebei, and is regarded as a pioneering work and a key source for the analysis of Hebei dance.

The above literature has longitudinally sorted out the history of Hebei from different perspectives, so that the author clearly understands the development of Hebei's history, the evolution of Hebei's dance, and clarifies the important position of Hebei's dance in the development of the whole Chinese dance, which has laid a good foundation for the subsequent analysis.

Conclusion

The geographical environment of Hebei is diverse, and the life and customs of each region are different, and the artistic characteristics of folk dances are also very different. Therefore, in the analysis of this thesis, folk dances with great artistic characteristics in each region are selected for detailed analysis. The folk dances in the urban areas of each region are represented by Changli Di Yangge, Jingfu Lahua, etc. This paper provides an overview of the historical origins of these art forms.

Hebei Yangge has a long history of development, and at the same time is relatively diverse in form, reproducing the life customs and cultural traditions of the people of Hebei. This art form was also created by the people of the region during a long period of daily accumulation, and has four distinctive characteristics. The first is spontaneity, the second is self-entertainment, the third is improvisation, and the fourth is stability, as Hebei Yangge has been passed down from generation to generation according to the natural law of its development. The ontological consciousness of Hebei Yangge is also changing with the forward development of history. The traditional Yangge dance grows on the cultivated land, and the artistic Yangge dance conveys the aesthetic

meaning. Regardless of the period in history, the art of dance is the carrier of cultural research, and sorting out the research content of Hebei Yangge ontology is an effective way to study the cultural form of Hebei Yangge.

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